

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON IMPROVING SOUND SIMILARITY MAPS WITH SEMANTIC METADATA

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Supervisor: Dr. Frederic Font, UPF

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Abstract

Searching and browsing appropriate sounds within large collections of audio samples can be challenging for musicians and sound designers. Most commonly, list-based search approaches are being used for displaying content for music production, however, several attempts have been made to improve user experience by projecting sounds on a two-dimensional map. These maps usually rely on dimensionality reduction methods like PCA, UMAP, or t-SNE to translate an audio embedding or another high dimensional feature representation into a low dimensional latent space, which typically involves a trade-off between the preservation of the global and local structure of the data. Providing metadata or custom distance measures to the algorithms can improve the clustering but requires correct labels and a solid feature representation. In this work, we address this issue by including user metadata for classification refinement of the audio to achieve an improved label description and post-process the point positions of the projection with the help of class probabilities. We conducted a comparative study of different map layouts to understand the usefulness of the aforementioned method to improve sound similarity projections. In our study, we found that hierarchically adding semantics and having a more concise local structure benefits both sound searching and explorational browsing. The methods presented in this thesis have potential applicability in other research domains involving classification and projection tasks.

Keywords: Sound similarity maps; Dimensionality reduction; Sample browsing

Chapter 1

Introduction

Contemporary music production often includes the usage of various libraries and collections of sound samples which are most commonly displayed in a list-based manner within digital audio workstations (DAW). Acquiring desired sounds require little effort for musicians due to online databases like Freesound¹ or Splice², however, searching and sorting these large amounts of samples can be a tedious task and introduces the need for an efficient and more user-friendly data representation. Although most audio editors provide graphical representations of musical content like real time visualizations of spectrograms and waveforms, it has only been in recent years that attempts have been made to improve sound searching and organization with visual approaches like two-dimensional sound maps. Visualizing sounds as objects based on their sonic properties originates from the field of psychoacoustics [1] and facilitates the construction of perceptual spaces. The rapid progress of sound visualization techniques was advanced by music information retrieval researchers, who proposed several methods for representational learning of audio and dimensionality reduction (DR) algorithms for projecting high-level data which will be covered in more detail in the next section.

In general, sound similarity maps follow a common pattern of how to display audio content. First, we achieve some sort of high-level feature representation of the

¹<https://freesound.org/>

²<https://splice.com/>

audio and then reduce the dimensionality to a 2D latent space based on the data's similarity. This has shown to be an efficient way of organizing and improving the browsing experience of large collections of audio samples. However, this method heavily depends on the feature representation and the hyperparameters chosen for the projection algorithm.

Further, we often do not consider any metadata like user tags or labels for correct classification - instead, we only trust the embedding of the audio signal. Additionally, the sole use of feature vectors will set the focus inevitably on sonic similarity without taking into account a proper hierarchical organization or folder structure of the sample collection. This raises the question of whether sound maps should focus on explorational browsing as creative support or specific sound searching in a large database or maybe both. Further, the requirements can even differ based on the sound content itself. Sound designers or foley artists may prefer locally labeled and structured clusters to effortlessly find desired sounds while musicians or composers would rather have a stronger global map layout with the focus on sonic similarity to boost their creative output.

Considering the above, we can observe that there is always a trade-off between the preservation of the global and local structure of the data, being advantageous for one or the other. Furthermore, improving the layout is usually done by preprocessing the audio for the best possible feature representation and classification through an embedding. However, automatic tagging and extraction networks can be prone to misclassification and are highly dependent on the audio signal quality which can result in unsatisfactory projection when feeding the mismatched labels to a DR algorithm. Additionally, most maps do not incorporate the aspect of organizing sounds categorically originally approached by tree-like structured search interfaces. In this thesis, we address the aforementioned problems and propose a new approach to improve the projection trade-off for the best possible sound mapping. This process can be divided into two sections: a classification refinement pre-process and a post-processing point position refinement. The classification refinement uses additional metadata like user tags, filenames, and class probabilities to estimate the most likely

label for the sound. This way we decrease the number of mismatched classes that are fed to the DR method. The class and class probabilities are obtained from the YAMNet model³, a pre-trained neural network that can classify sound events from 521 classes based on the AudioSet corpus [2]. The AudioSet ontology is a hierarchical collection of audio events which was used for the class estimation. The user tags are obtained from Freesound, an open-source repository for audio samples developed and maintained by the University Pompeu Fabra (UPF). The latter implies that the refinement is only feasible when metadata is available. However, this limitation can be neglected for most modern libraries since even commercial cloud databases for audio content like Splice or Loopcloud⁴ provide additional metadata like tags or keywords.

Despite refining the class estimation, we propose a method to adjust the reduced point positions based on the computed class probabilities relating to a hierarchical label layout. This way, we obtain (linearly) regulated local clusters that enhance the class belongings of each point per category. To evaluate the projections, we conducted a comparative study on several distinct map layouts displayed in an interface adaption of an existing prototype for visualizing sound maps⁵. The user tests are separated into two subtasks: a specific sound searching approach where users had to find a fixed target sound and an explorational search task where users should find similar sounds based on a target sample. The reasoning behind the aforementioned tasks will be covered in detail in the user evaluation section.

Our main contributions are (1) using user semantics for class estimation to improve projections, and (2) using class probabilities for cluster regulation of the two-dimensional layout. Both methods are fairly trivial tasks that need further development left for future work, however, demonstrate the applicability of semantics and hierarchical layouts for sound similarity maps.

³<https://tfhub.dev/google/yamnet/1>

⁴<https://www.loopcloud.com/cloud/>

⁵<https://github.com/ffont/sound-map-visualizer>

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Browsing appropriate sounds within large collections of audio samples can be challenging for musicians and sound designers. Most digital audio workstations (DAW) provide list-based search options to organize media, while third-party software offers alternative browsing methods where sound files are projected within a two-dimensional map. In this chapter, we cover the state of the art on how to map sounds in a 2D latent space that usually includes audio analysis for feature representation and dimensionality reduction for data projection.

2.1 Feature representation

Displaying audio data requires an appropriate feature representation of the analyzed signals. Extracting audio descriptors is a well-studied topic in music information retrieval research (MIR), providing several open-source libraries for audio analysis [3, 4] as well as deep embeddings [5] for high-level representations. Despite several approaches for feature retrieval, the common aim is to achieve a suitable numerical sound description. Audio features are mainly computations of spectral, time-domain, rhythmic, and tonal features based on signal processing algorithms or high-level descriptors like neural network embeddings.

Computing low-level features is fast and efficient, however, multi-categorical vari-

ables introduce dimensionality problems. Several methods and algorithms have been proposed for DR and feature selection which will be covered in the following sections. Applications of machine learning have seen a significant increase in recent years, in particular the use of deep learning embeddings which map discrete variables to continuous feature vectors. This technique has gathered attention within the MIR research community especially for generating meaningful audio feature representations that lower the dimensionality of categorical descriptors.

Embeddings are often used in favor of high-cardinality variables where training a machine learning model would be infeasible due to the unmanageable dimensionality. However, since embeddings are learned parameters (weights) of a neural network, computation times are longer compared to low-level feature extraction which needs to be taken into account depending on the application's performance requirements. Furthermore, feature representation through deep embeddings is more suitable for classification tasks using neural networks because of the network's difficulty with categorical features. Other classification tasks may outperform embeddings depending on the model. The data preprocessing by using feature selection or transformation is commonly known as dimensionality reduction which will be covered in the next section.

2.2 Dimensionality reduction and feature selection

As mentioned above, audio descriptions often contain a large number of features, thus considered high dimensional data. While embeddings already introduce a method of lowering the data cardinality, further techniques are trying to optimize analysis accuracy. Besides an increase of training or classification times for high dimensional feature representations, there are several other reasons like the interpretability and identification of reduced feature sets or removing noisy and irrelevant features why DR may improve a model's performance. Further, data is more likely to be indistinguishable when represented by high dimensional descriptors which harm similarity measures.

Dimension reduction can apply to supervised or unsupervised learning with either feature selection or feature transformation. Common techniques are principal component analysis (PCA) [6], linear discriminant analysis (LDA) [7], autoencoder neural networks [8] as well as UMAP [9] or t-SNE [10] for visualization purposes of categorical data e.g. for clustering into a 2D latent space. Principal component analysis is an unsupervised feature transformation technique that characterizes objects by computing uncorrelated variables (a mixture of the initial variables) with maximum variance, the so-called principal components. It attempts to 'squeeze' the information of the initial variables into the first significant components by computing eigenvectors of a covariance matrix and sorting them in descending order. However, PCA requires data standardization and may decrease data interpretability and readability due to information loss. Linear discriminant analysis can be considered as the feature transforming counterpart to PCA when reducing supervised data dimensionality - training data with attached class labels. The purpose of LDA is to achieve a good feature transformation for class separation instead of maximizing data variance as PCA does. Possible disadvantages of LDA are the normal distribution requirement for the feature set and a decreased performance for a few categorical variables.

The third common reduction technique is a three-layered neural network called an autoencoder which lowers dimensionality by restricting the number of hidden layer nodes (the encoder part of the networks) to achieve a compressed representation of the input variables [8]. Autoencoders are significantly slower than e.g. PCA and LDA but provide the ability to reduce dimensionality for large datasets that exceed memory space by batching the input data to overcome memory limitations. Even though the aforementioned algorithms are used for data visualization, reduction techniques have been proposed that are particularly well suited for 2D and 3D projections. T-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE), a variation of Stochastic Neighbor Embedding [11], is reducing high dimensional data by converting datapoint similarities to joint probabilities and minimizing the divergence between the distribution of the pairwise similarities of the high and low dimensional points respectively [10]. This technique is computationally expensive and often re-

quires another dimension reduction like PCA to be applied before using t-SNE.

Another nonlinear reduction method is the Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) [9] which tries to project the low dimensional data with the closest possible equivalent fuzzy topological structure of the manifold. Similar to t-SNE, it is a graph-based algorithm that constructs a high dimensional weighted graph and then optimizes the lower dimensional layout. Several attempts have been made to compare the performances and suitability of different reduction algorithms regarding accuracy and efficiency [10, 11]. Defining quality assessment criteria for dimensionality reduction can be challenging and often does not propose distinct answers for which algorithms should be preferred. Common evaluation tasks entail comparisons of minimum loss of data quality and computation time. An important objective of projection algorithms like t-SNE or UMAP is the trade-off between providing a good local or global topological structure of the low dimensional representation. A global structure refers to the perseverance of the relative neighborhood positions, while a local structure tries to preserve the best possible representation of each observation's neighborhood. This needs to be considered depending on the application of the mapping algorithm.

As shown in [12], t-SNE and UMAP provide a good local structure while techniques like PaCMAP and TriMap [13] preserve a better global representation. t-SNE and UMAP are stochastic models and both highly dependent on the choice of hyperparameters which can achieve different results in different iterations. Both algorithms are considered 'near-sighted' as they only pay attention to neighbors while disregarding further points in the high dimensional which does not maintain a good global structure.

[12] proposes Pairwise Controlled Manifold Approximation Projection (PaCMAP), an improved algorithm for dimension reduction that tries to preserve both global and local representations. The authors tested several DR algorithms on twelve different dataset showing that PaCMAP outperforms UMAP and t-SNE regarding computation time. In contrast to the aforementioned methods, PaCMAP puts more emphasis on the mid near points of the high-dimensional data and considers the

Figure 1: DR algorithm visualizations of Mammoth dataset [12]

neighbors later. The main idea is to incorporate forces for further points which are neglected by algorithms like t-SNE and UMAP which leads to ignoring the global structure. Further PaCMAP does not require PCA initialization for preserving a more stable global representation of the low dimensional embedding which we can observe in Figure 1. However, current PaCMAP implementations do not include supervised learning by incorporating labels. Instead, we decided to use the comprehensive UMAP library¹ to surpass this issue.

2.3 Software products

With recent improvements in machine learning and dimensional analysis, the audio industry has proposed several software products focusing on sample visualization for file browsing and music production. However, most software relies on some of the

¹<https://github.com/lmcinnes/umap>

mentioned dimension reduction techniques for low dimensional visualization, approaches differ a lot across the available implementations. Figure 2 shows a general workflow graph of sound similarity maps.

Figure 2: A common workflow of sound similarity maps

As mentioned above, a common toolchain for visualizing audio data involves a high-dimensional representation of the sound files achieved through several feature extraction approaches like low-level descriptor extraction or by using low-dimensional neural network embeddings. Besides extracting information from audio, it is crucial to select features that represent the data in the best possible way. Several attempts have been made trying to visualize audio samples in a 2D space based on the timbral properties [14, 15]. The Freesound Explorer [14] allows users to query sounds from the Freesound API² and project them by their timbral similarity and a calculated tristimulus descriptor that sets the color of the point for the visualization.

Furthermore, Audio Commons developed a model to predict different timbral classifiers like hardness, depth, brightness, roughness, warmth, sharpness, boominess, and reverb which is demonstrated by Timbral Explorer [15] where the user can select two attributes for the x and y point positions respectively to create a similarity map for sample exploration. A big advantage of displaying the data with precomputed attributes is that it is fast to calculate and provides a reasonable cluster for small datasets. However, projecting larger collections of sounds can result in a confusing layout since the coloring of the points solely relies on two different parameters. Further, this visualization method is not able to display multiple clusters of e.g. different sound classes which negatively affects its suitability for bigger datasets.

²<https://freesound.org/docs/api/>

Often we have to find patterns and similarities for multidimensional data which has the advantage of being able to achieve a better data point distinction but also introduces the problem of dimensionality and feature selection. Thus, many approaches have moved away from displaying data solely based on single attributes or manually selected feature descriptors and instead make use of mapping algorithms to reduce dimensionality while preserving the data's structure. Soundtorch [16], a prototype using the most popular approach of Self-organizing maps (SOM) [17] to project computed Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) [18] on a 2D layout. [16] evaluated different distance metrics (Euclidean, Mahalanobis, and Cosine) where the Cosine distance worked the best. The prototype focuses on providing an interactive playground for the user to identify the sound in a spatial layout which enhances the browsing experience. Because of its architecture, it is more suitable for exploring sounds in a local structure and therefore lacks a good global representation of the sound collection.

Further attempts like AudioQuilt [19] introduce the usage of kernelized sorting [20] which achieves a 1-to-1 mapping between samples and the corresponding locations in the grid. They also use metric learning to preserve the euclidean assumption of dimensionality equality and independence of the multidimensional input feature space and refine the distance measure. The proposed prototypes include a snare navigator where the samples are represented by rectangles in a grid with the proximity representing the sound similarity and a synth explorer that provides an interface where the users can specify their grid setup which will be mapped based on different synthesizer parameters and the corresponding sound similarity of the samples.

Further attempts of user customization in terms of visualization of the browsing topology and audio tagging have been made by researchers of Belmont University and Art+Log Inc. [21] proposes Vibrary, a user-trainable neural network for audio tagging with user-specific and customizable tags. The user provides a dataset for spectral analysis, so the spectrograms can be used to train the network. This analysis process happens client side while the training is done on the server side to overcome calculation barriers. Then, the server returns the corresponding weights

for the network. Thus the client can add additional audio files which are then run locally on the network with the previously downloaded weights, so the user can personalize tags for the dataset. Proposing a tagging utility for audio tagging is an appealing approach for sorting samples and improving file browsing, however, it may not be suitable for large amounts of data due to the computational complexity of analyzing spectrograms and training a neural network. Furthermore, this approach only incorporates tags for classification but neglects other important features of the audio to improve similarity searching.

Sononym [22] makes use of the aforementioned audio tagging approach but provides further analysis to help users find similar sounds of their collection based on any source sound input. This standalone application offers an interface to display audio by tags in a two-dimensional cluster or a list-based search with similarity ranking. With regards to the aforementioned concerns, the audio industry provided several products trying to optimize file browsing visualization with different mapping approaches. Software like XO by XLN [23], Atlas by Algonaut [24] extend the idea of 2D file browsing by focusing on offering the user the ability to explore (mostly) drum samples that can be used with the internal drum sequencer to achieve more intuitive music making. While XO only clusters all data points and adds colors for similar classes, Atlas provides additional labeling on top of the 2D grid, so the user knows where to find which sample class before exploring the individual sounds. However, the tagging system of Atlas does not include user specifics like folder names or custom tags. Therefore, besides having a decent similarity map view, the textual labels are often incorrect.

A proof of concept for modern 2D file browsers is AudioStellar [25], which, similar to the software mentioned above, projects the audio data as points in a two-dimensional space. The process includes audio analysis (computing spectrograms of converted mono files and getting one vector for each audio file), PCA to achieve better performance for t-SNE mapping as described in the dimensionality reduction section, and then doing Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) [26] to find and colorize the corresponding subclusters. This fairly easy

concept achieves a good mapping result with more isolated clusters than XO and also provides the ability to rearrange points in the latent space. However, it faces the same issue of scalability, as bigger datasets result in a gigantic map that might even decrease the intuitive approach of optimizing similarity search.

COSMOS by Waves [27], one of the most recent software products for 2D sample browsing, combines several mapping layouts into one standalone application. It analyzes the audio, writes the metadata to an SQL database, and then uses different pre-trained models for classification and creates five different maps for the user to choose from. Besides the mapping view, the user has the option to find samples in a list-based search where files can be sorted by tags and timbral features. COSMOS analyzes 122 sound classes with one named 'unknown' for bad classifications. While the tagging system works well and improves the file search, the two-dimensional maps do not include the label tags or any semantics to optimize sample projection.

Chapter 3

Methodology

As shown in the previous chapters, sound similarity maps usually rely on DR algorithms to reduce the feature dimension of the audio embedding. This concept has proven to be quite efficient for visualization but also imposes a burden of choosing the right hyperparameters for the best possible projection. Further, a bad audio classification can negatively affect the mapping. To surpass these problems, we propose two methods of refinement tasks to achieve a map layout with a focus on local subclusters and a global categorical structure, and an improved semantic description.

3.1 Dataset

For the sake of this thesis, it was convenient to use open-source audio content of Freesound due to available metadata and licensing issues. Specifically, we used the evaluation subset of the FSD50K dataset with over 10000 human-labeled sound events unequally distributed in 200 classes based on the AudioSet Ontology [2]. The audio content contains mainly natural sounds from physical sound sources like human or animal sounds as well as 'sound of things' and musical instruments. A big benefit of the dataset is its suitability for the YAMNet model which can predict 521 classes of the AudioSet corpus and computes the embedding for the feature representation. The evaluation subset contains a total of 10231 audio samples that were fed into the YAMNet network. We used the containerized YAMNet analyzer

of Freesound to compute the embeddings directly from the audio file and saved the analysis data in JSON format. The analyzer returns a vector of class probabilities following the percentage strategy [28] and the embedding mean calculated across all audio frames. The class with the highest probability is considered the active class. From 10231 samples, we obtained 9093 true embeddings and 1138 null embeddings. Further, we rejected samples with a class value count of less than 30 per category to end up with a well-distributed subset of 6843 audio files for the interface.

3.2 General overview

The methodology comprises two separate approaches to enhance sound projections in a two-dimensional space. A general overview of the workflow can be found in Figure 3. The preprocessing part defines the refinement of the class estimation before the DR algorithm while the post-processing section describes the 2D point adjustment of the algorithm’s output. Ideally, both techniques would be done before or by the DR method but mainly expose an implementation issue that would be out of the scope of this work which will be covered in detail in the conclusion section.

As an initial starting point, we computed class probabilities and embeddings and extracted the necessary metadata (user tags, filenames, Freesound ID) from the analysis data of the dataset for all audio samples. Additionally, the audio and metadata are accessible through the Freesound API. Instead of feeding the embedding and the corresponding class to the DR algorithm, we conduct a class refinement task to estimate the correct label which will result in an improved projection. For this work, we used the UMAP algorithm due to ease of use, especially with the option of inputting labels along with the embedding. Anyhow, other DR methods mentioned in the previous chapter are eligible as well. Furthermore, we focus on demonstrating the practicality of adding semantics to the map layout along with improving DR and a precise local structure instead of proposing a different DR algorithm. In the post-processing section, we adjusted the point positions retrieved from UMAP based on the class probabilities to achieve a more compressed local structure in exchange for a decreased similarity layout. This approach is a quite brute force method which ex-

Figure 3: A general overview of the workflow including class and point refinements

poses several issues addressed later in this chapter. For a baseline model of the user evaluation interface, we computed reference maps by only considering the YAMNet embedding and its corresponding active class before the refinement for the UMAP projection. This approximates the state-of-the-art approach that only considers automatic tagging and projection without including semantic metadata or post-process point adjustment. This way, we achieve a realistic model for comparison.

3.3 Class refinement

As mentioned above, an objective of this work is to evaluate user preferences for a categorical structure in the global space and a sound similarity mapping in the local field which presumes a meaningful class hierarchy like the AudioSet ontology. The AudioSet corpus contains 632 classes organized in a hierarchical manner with up

to six layers. The first two layers consist of 7 and 43 classes respectively. Figure 4 shows the first two layers of the ontology. Those classes are only used for categorical assignment of lower layer classes but were not set as an active class for the individual samples. This way we can get accurate local clusters since we only consider classes lower than the third layer and a good global structure by feeding the first layer parent classes to the DR algorithm.

Figure 4: The first two hierarchy layers of the AudioSet ontology adapted from [2]

The refinement of the class estimation comprises four steps in hierarchical order as shown in Figure 5. The main objective is to return the most likely label based on user metadata and the classifier’s output. Therefore we conceptualized an automatic voting mechanism that weighs up the class by using semantic information. The YAMNet model outputs probabilities for 25 classes in descending order, declaring the class with the highest value as the active class of the embedding. First, we evaluate the accuracy of the active class prediction based on a threshold value. We have set a threshold of 85%, meaning that if the embedding predicts a label with a probability of more than 85% we can confidently select the initial class. This value of 85% has no theoretical ground, however, should serve the purpose of

Figure 5: The workflow of improving the class estimation with semantic information

defining a threshold for when to trust the model’s prediction. If the latter condition is not fulfilled, we move on to a primitive string comparison of user tags and the ontology classes of the third layer. User metadata is usually biased and sometimes contains baffling information which is hard to interpret. However, considering the previous refinement step as an automatic gatekeeper for the classification, we can optimistically do the semantic analysis.

Throughout this task, we follow the simple paradigm of ‘a wrong label cannot be more wrong’. The string comparison compares the textual occurrences of any of the tags in one of the third layer classes: a user tag like ‘rain’ will result in the class estimation of the label ‘Rain’. This ideal scenario is not often the case, which leads us to the next step of the refinement process. This approach is fairly simple, however, tries to surpass the issue of semantic errors. First, we conduct a value count for the class probabilities to see which third layer class bucket is the most likely one. For all children of this third layer class, we compute the Levenshtein distances for each user tag. The Levenshtein distance is a metric for string approximation that measures the similarity between two input strings, that counts the number of transforms required to create the target from the source string [6]. A user tag like ‘raain’ compared to the label ‘Rain’ will result in a Levenshtein distance of two, as we solely need

to remove the letter 'a' and transform 'r' to uppercase. Afterward, we select the class with minimal distance and repeat this process for each user tag. Lastly, we receive the class estimate by selecting the majority class (the class with the most occurrences). Certainly, this approach faces several drawbacks as we only consider the string representation and not its 'perceptual' meaning. It would be interesting to see if natural language processing approaches could surpass this problem and achieve more accurate results. However, this proposal is out of scope for this work and is open to future research.

3.4 2D Point position adjustment

The objective of the point adjustment is that sounds that belong to the same categorical class should be located close to each other despite their sonic similarity. Hence, we emphasize local clusters for lower class layers of the hierarchy. The reason for this is that we want to investigate if sound similarity maps should be balanced more towards the sample organization side rather than solely focusing on projections of audio feature comparability. The refinement process iteratively adjusts the point positions as shown in Figure 6. For full implementation details and explanations, we refer the reader to the published source code¹.

First, we compute the centroid positions of each cluster of the third layer of the ontology to get an estimate of the local density. Then we calculate the distance between the points and the centroid position to find the furthest point away from the cluster which still belongs to the parent label (third layer). Next, we look at the class probabilities of the corresponding sound and compute the average of the probabilities that belong to the parent label. This percentage determines the relative amount of displacement of the point towards the centroid position. Assuming a sound with class probabilities containing 'Pigeon, dove', 'Crow' and 'Owl' with values '0.45', '0.3', '0.1' respectively would result in a total displacement of 85% of the distance closer to the centroid position of the parent class 'Bird'. Following this we recompute the centroid position and repeat the process. Adjusting the positions simultaneously

¹<https://github.com/lennartnicolas/smc-master-thesis>

Figure 6: The workflow of adjusting the point position for a cluster

would result in a fixed centroid position which would be a reasonable approach as well. The amount of iterations is dependent on the value count of the points of each label. In summary, the point refinement yields more local non-diffuse clustering for the subcategories of the parent class. A drawback of this method is the problem of too dense clusters when adjusting points that are already close to each other. However, this exposes an implementation issue only. Ideally, the whole process would be done before the DR by e.g. defining custom distance metrics and adjusting hyperparameters based on class probabilities that fit the aforementioned approach.

3.5 Color schemes

Typically sound similarity maps contain some sort of color scheme to distinguish between the different classes of sounds. Since sounds are represented as dots in a two-dimensional plane, individual colors for each label show the corresponding class belonging. As mentioned earlier, this thesis focuses on understanding projection methods rather than extensive research on colormaps or other user interfaces related concepts. However, we like to briefly cover certain aspects relating to the color layout

Figure 7: The workflow of generating color schemes based on the parent palette

of the proposed sound maps. An objective of colorizing the sound objects is to easily distinguish between different classes. At first, this seems like a trivial task but bears a scalability problem when having a large number of labels. The research field of distinctive color spaces is extensively studied [29, 30] and proposes several methods or fixed color palettes with maximized contrast or distance metrics like CIEDE-2000 [31] to measure distinctiveness between colors. Complementing this thesis, we hierarchically fit the color layout for the first three ontology layers. We approached the color scheme the same way we laid out the map. To separate the high-level categories in the global space, the first layer colors approximate maximum contrast and are selected from this 16-color palette [32]. For the second and third layers, we generated maximum contrasted color schemes based on the parent class color by computing near RGB colors regarding a distance threshold. The aforementioned concept is shown in Figure 7. We justify this approach by stating that classes with similar parents should follow a common color pattern while high-level categories should have maximum contrast to facilitate organization and navigation of the sound collection.

In summary, this method solves the purpose but is far from thoroughly studied. Additionally, the main drawback of color schemes is the exclusion of people with bad vision or color blindness. Using different shapes for classification might be an appealing approach that is left for future research.

3.6 User evaluation

Our main objective is to evaluate the adjusted projection approach in comparison to a base model that solely relies on the DR of the embedding like used by most state-of-the-art sound similarity maps. Further, we want to examine the applicability of semantics added to the layout to facilitate sound searching and exploration.

3.6.1 Background

Before diving into the structure of the evaluation tasks, we will briefly cover the different perspectives on the characteristics of two-dimensional sound maps. It is needless to say that sound designers, musicians, or foley artists have varying requirements in the process of 2D sample browsing. While the musician may prefer a map with all of their sounds organized by sonic similarity as a creative tool to make music, the sound designer would rather have a more structured layout with labels and dense clusters to easily find specific samples for setting a movie to music.

Even though there are plenty of different usage scenarios, we categorized the evaluation into two main branches: (1) searching for specific content and (2) explorational searching for unknown content. Furthermore, only a little research has been done to investigate if sound similarity maps should be balanced more towards the organization of large collections of samples in a two-dimensional space to overcome the limitations of scroll lists or should solely display sounds based on their sonic properties. With this user evaluation structure, we aim to shed some light on that topic.

3.6.2 User tasks

For the evaluation of the projection method, we conducted user tests of two tasks performed on two different layouts for the base model and the refined map. As explained in the methodology section, the base model refers to a state-of-the-art approach using UMAP for the embedding and the YAMNet active class without any further adjustments. The participants had to perform the tasks on a local web

Figure 8: The interface and map layouts for each task

interface and answer the corresponding questionnaire. The interface is an adaptation of Frederic Fonts’ sound map visualizer² that features the map layouts for the evaluation and projects the sounds as colored circles on a 2D plane similar to most state-of-the-art applications as shown in Figure 8. We implemented basic controls for navigation and audio playback as well as the color schemes and semantic information for the first three layers of the ontology based on the zoom level. This way we only plot seven different colors in the global scope (small zoom level) that represent the sounds belonging to the first layer of the hierarchy. The placement of

²<https://github.com/ffont/sound-map-visualizer>

the labels is determined by the centroid position of all points corresponding to the class. When zooming into the map, the lower layer color schemes will be displayed to achieve a top-to-bottom search effect that should demonstrate the approach of setting the focus on sound organization in the global scope as shown in Figure 9. It is important to state that the interface itself should not be taken into account for the evaluation of the maps. This prototype solely serves the purpose of providing a straightforward application to interact with the different projections that are suitable for user tests.

(1) Second layer classes and colors

(2) Third layer classes and colors

Figure 9: The second (1) and third (2) layer centroid class displayed dependent on the zoom level

As mentioned above, the participants had to perform two different tasks on two pairs of maps which results in a total of eight projections. All eight maps have distinct layouts with the same sound content and were set up in pairs base model/refined model for the individual task. The UMAP hyperparameters are similar for each model despite the random state to achieve variant projections. The first pair contained no semantics on the map, while the second pair did.

For the first task, users had to find a fixed target sound within the corresponding map. Each of the four maps had a different target sound. For the second task, the participants had to find up to three similar sounding samples based on a fixed

target sound. Similar to the first task, each map contained a separate target sample. With this division of evaluation tasks, we get a good estimate of the usefulness of the refined projection and if semantic information is beneficial for sample browsing in a two-dimensional space. While performing the tasks, the participants had to fill out a questionnaire which is shown in Table 1. The evaluation comprises questions about the task accomplishment, colors, and semantics of the maps. The main objective was to get a general understanding of the user experience to compare each map layout.

ID	Question	Metric
Q1	Have you been able to find the sound? / Have you been able to find enough sounds?	Yes / No
Q2	It was easy for me to find the target sound. / It was easy for me to find a satisfying amount of similar sounds.	Likert scale (1-5)
Q3	The color schemes helped me guiding through the map.	Likert scale (1-5)
Q4	Sounds that were close to each other in the map sounded similar.	Likert scale (1-5)
Q5	The semantics (labels) helped me guiding through the map. [Note: only for maps with labels added]	Likert scale (1-5)
Q6	How did you approach finding the sound/s and why? Please describe the searching process as precisely as possible.	Open question

Table 1: Questionnaire for each map layout of the user evaluation interface

Demographic information was rejected from the questionnaire due to irrelevance. First, we wanted to gather information about the accomplishment of the task and the usefulness of the color schemes, and, depending on the map, the displayed labels. We used the Likert scale metric to assess Q2-Q5 to get a reasonable representation of the applicability of the respective map. For our comparative study, we focused on evaluating the 'ease of use' for each layout to investigate which map aids the searching tasks the most. Since the projection adjustment resulted in more dense local clusters, we examined its effect on the sound similarity of the layout (Q4). Further, we evaluated the usefulness of semantics within the projection (Q5) and their impact on the searching process. To make assumptions about what and how

map-characteristics affect user experience, users had to answer an open question on their workflow/process of finding the target samples. The open question (Q6) helped justify and understand the scores of Q1-Q5 and find patterns in how users approached the different layouts. The questions were set up in the way that users scored the map first before going into detail and describing their searching approach. This way the participants provide a more brief evaluation of the general impression of the map and focus on assessing specific characteristics and observations at the end of the task.

Chapter 4

Results

In this section, we present the results of the user evaluation tasks as described above. The evaluation was conducted by a total of five participants with backgrounds in music technology. Considering the small number of candidates we rejected significance tests and cannot solely rely on the statistics of the Likert scale questions and will put more emphasis on analyzing how the users described their process of approaching the tasks with the corresponding map.

4.1 User task 1

First, we present the results of comparing the refined projection (first map) and the base model (second map) without labels. The maps were labeled consecutively for each task (M1.1 - M1.4 and M2.1 - M2.4). As shown in Figure 10, all participants were able to find the sound in the refined map layout, however, only 80% could accomplish the task with the basic state-of-the-art approach. Further, we can observe that it was subjectively easier to find the target sound in the adjusted projection than in the base model with an average rating of 2.8/5 compared to 2.6/5.

However, the color schemes of the refined model were less helpful with an average score of 3/5 and 3.6/5. In addition, both maps were evaluated equally in terms of sound similarity, meaning sounds located close to each other had the same perceptual resemblance. Regarding the searching process, we can observe a common

Figure 10: The results of the questionnaire for maps M1.1 - M1.4 for user task (1); Q1: 'Have you been able to find the sound?'; Q2: 'It was easy for me to find the target sound.'; Q3: 'The color schemes helped me guiding through the map.'; Q4: 'Sounds that were close to each other in the map sounded similar.'; Q5: 'The semantics (labels) helped me guiding through the map.'

pattern on how users approached both maps. First, participants reported that they tried to get a general overview of the map by visiting different clusters with one user specifically pointing out that the precise local clusters of the first map and the distances in between supported the navigation process. Further, one user mentioned that changing color schemes depending on the zoom level was 'irritating' and 'misleading'. After identifying a similar category compared to the target sound, participants began navigating that cluster. However, they pointed out that it was difficult to detect a certain pattern in how the sounds were laid out, so they had to visit each point of the cluster separately. For the base model, one user reported

that despite finding a cluster of sounds, they were not able to find the target sound nearby. Furthermore, it is worth noting that users had a better understanding of the overall interface and projections after accomplishing the task on the first map. Still, the refined projection achieved slightly better results than the basic UMAP approach.

The following paragraph covers the results of comparing the refined projection (first map) and the base model (second map) with labels added to the maps. As mentioned in the methodology section, labels were displayed at the centroid position of all points corresponding to the class. Since the base model solely relies on the classes of the embedding, several sounds are misclassified which therefore leads to a displaced centroid. This problem confuses as we can observe in the user feedback. For the refined map, all users were able to find the sound while for the base model only 20% of the participants could accomplish the task.

Understandably, the reports show that it was easier to find the target sound in the first map than in the second one with an average score of 3.8/5 and 1.4/5 respectively. The color schemes of the refined projection were more helpful to the users with an average score of 3.6/5 compared to 2.4/5 for the base model. The sound similarity of the map was evaluated fairly equally with an average of 4.4/5 and 4.2/5. All participants pointed out that the descriptive labels heavily improved the search experience for the refined map, while the semantics of the base model were utterly confusing. The users utilized the labeled groups to aid their search and after finding the desired label, they began looking for similar samples to the target sound.

4.2 User task 2

This section presents the results of the second task for the first pair of maps without semantic information added to the projections. For this task users should explore the map and subjectively find similar samples for three different target sounds per map. The evaluation shows that 80% of the participants were able to find enough sounds on the first map, while only 60% could locate enough samples on the second

Figure 11: The results of the questionnaire for maps M2.1 - M2.4 for user task (2); Q1: 'Have you been able to find enough sounds?'; Q2: 'It was easy for me to find a satisfying amount of similar sounds.'; Q3: 'The color schemes helped me guiding through the map.'; Q4: 'Sounds that were close to each other in the map sounded similar.'; Q5: 'The semantics (labels) helped me guiding through the map.'

map. However, finding satisfying sounds was reported to be more successful with the base model than with the refined projection with an average of 3.0/5 compared to 3.6/5. Due to the small number of participants, this can be considered a slight difference. The color schemes were more helpful in the first map with an average score of 3.6/5 in contrast to 3.0/5 for the base model. As shown in Figure 11 and similar to the previous map pairs, the sound similarity was evaluated fairly equally for both projections.

However, users positively described the layout of the map stating that overlapping/similar sounds from different styles were mapped close to each other. Similar

to the previous task, the participants attempted the searching process by randomly navigating through different clusters to get a better understanding of the global layout before diving into thematically similar sound groups. In summary, there is no clear candidate for which map the users preferred to accomplish the explorational task. Lastly, we cover the results of the map-pair containing semantic information. Similar to the previous map pair, 80% of the participants found enough sounds in the refined projection and 60% in the base model. However, both maps were reported to be equally difficult to search through and find satisfying results. The color schemes were evaluated as slightly more helpful for the refined map than for the base model with an average score of 3.8/5 and 3.4/5 respectively. Again, the semantics within the map were particularly supportive for navigation of the first map but were reported as 'missing' or 'misplaced' for the base model. However, they seemed to be more helpful than in the first task as the responses for the usefulness of the labels were higher with an average rating of 4.4/5 for the unrefined map and 4.2/5 for the adjusted projection. Further, a few users pointed out that displaying the labels based on the zoom level was confusing as it negatively affected the orientation within the map. In summary, the refined model received a slightly better review than the base model.

4.3 Evaluation drawbacks

Before analyzing the results we address several issues that affect the overall conclusion of the proposed method of projection. First, we need to take into account the small number of participants which compromises the evaluation analysis. Furthermore, the users reported interface-related complaints (e.g. changing color schemes or displaying different labels based on the zoom level) which shall not be the focus of the evaluation, however, affected the user experience. Additionally, the FSD50K dataset comprises mostly natural sounds with a small subset of musical orientated samples. Therefore understanding the structure of the sound similarity map from a perceptual perspective is a challenging task, especially for inharmonic and noisy sounds. However, using different datasets would probably cause a classification

as the YAMNet model predicts only classes of the AudioSet ontology. Furthermore, our method heavily relies on the hierarchical approach for sound similarity maps and therefore is dependent on a certain ontology. Unfortunately, we are not aware of other state-of-the-art class hierarchy models like AudioSet based on more musical-related labels. In addition, we could observe that users were treating the explorational search similar to the first task. To have more transparency it would be beneficial to conduct a third test, where the participants should create a musical piece and report their subjective opinion on each map. However, this would be out of the scope and is left for future research.

4.4 Results analysis

This section summarizes our findings from the user evaluation. Despite the map layout, semantic information within the projection significantly aided the searching process for both tasks. As mentioned above, the displaced labels of the base model were heavily misleading which shows the classification improvement achieved by the refinement process. Even though the point adjustment based on the class probabilities was supporting the specific sound search, it negatively affected the sound similarity as reported by some of the participants. However, we could observe that the general perceptual layout for all maps was not ideal due to the variety of noisy and inharmonic samples. Furthermore, users approached both tasks in the same manner by trying to get a general overview of the global clusters first and then diving into subcategories. This is a clear indication that hierarchical layouts with semantic information aid the user experience for sound similarity maps, especially for large collections of sounds. Additionally, we found no significant results for the effectiveness of the proposed color layout of the projection. In summary, we can conclude that the refined projection with labels achieved the best ratings and reviews, while the base model with labels was its counterpart which mainly confused the participants and did not aid the browsing experience for both tasks.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In this section, we are concluding and proposing topics for future research based on the findings of the development and evaluation of this work. Sample browsing in a two-dimensional plane comprises various factors like the map layout, sound content, or interface interaction which differently affect the user experience. Further, depending on the searching task, we require separate weightings of these factors. Users that prefer a map solely for exploratory and creative purposes, will favor a layout focusing on the sonic properties (e.g. timbral similarity), while users that want to quickly find specific samples would go for a projection with a more categorical layout similar to a folder structure. However, we could observe that for both tasks of the evaluation users similarly navigated the mappings. Our interpretation of the latter suggests that similarity maps of large sound collections should set focus on a hierarchical organization instead of arranging samples solely based on their audio similarity. This tradeoff can be significant for the user experience depending on the sound content: noisy and percussive data is perceptually difficult to distinguish which can be tedious when searching for specific sound classes and no label structure is applied to the map layout. Within the scope of this thesis, we developed an adjusted projection by using semantic information in the form of user tags and a hierarchical class structure that facilitates user experience. Our approach requires additional metadata for each sound which is not always provided by

creators of sample content. To this point, our projection method is limited to data from the Freesound repository or any equivalent resource that provides user-specific tags. Furthermore, we structured the map hierarchy based on the AudioSet ontology which mainly comprises natural sound events and does not include any synthetic classes of (electronic) music categories. This drawback might have affected the explorational task results since users were provided with mostly non-musical samples. Future research should address different ontologies and datasets of more synthetic content. Additionally, we briefly covered the issue of colorizing sound objects based on the hierarchical class structure which bore no noteworthy findings in regards to user experience. However, this topic is considered a more interface-related problem which was not within the scope of this thesis. In conclusion, structuring sound similarity maps toward the hierarchical organization of sound content in the global space and precise local clusters obtained preferable results in terms of user experience compared to the conventional state-of-the-art layouts. Furthermore, semantic information aids the sample browsing process when labeled accurately. Finally, including user-related metadata for audio tagging can improve classification.

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Bibliography

- [1] Cooper, M., Foote, J., Pampalk, E. & Tzanetakis, G. Visualization in Audio-Based Music Information Retrieval. *Computer Music Journal* **30**, 42–62 (2006).
- [2] Gemmeke, J. F. *et al.* Audio Set: An ontology and human-labeled dataset for audio events. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 776–780 (IEEE, 2017).
- [3] Bogdanov, D. *et al.* ESSENTIA: an open-source library for sound and music analysis. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Multimedia*, 855–858 (ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2013).
- [4] McFee, B. *et al.* librosa: Audio and Music Signal Analysis in Python. 18–24 (2015).
- [5] Cramer, J., Wu, H.-H., Salamon, J. & Bello, J. P. Look, Listen, and Learn More: Design Choices for Deep Audio Embeddings. In *ICASSP 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 3852–3856 (IEEE, 2019).
- [6] Jolliffe, I. T. & Cadima, J. Principal component analysis: a review and recent developments. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* **374**, 20150202 (2016).
- [7] Tharwat, A., Gaber, T., Ibrahim, A. & Hassanien, A. E. Linear discriminant analysis: A detailed tutorial. *AI Communications* **30**, 169–190 (2017).
- [8] Bank, D., Koenigstein, N. & Giryes, R. Autoencoders (2020).

- [9] McInnes, L., Healy, J. & Melville, J. UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction (2018). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1802.03426>.
- [10] van der Maaten, L. & Hinton, G. Visualizing data using t-SNE. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **9**, 2579–2605 (2008).
- [11] Hinton, G. E. & Roweis, S. Stochastic Neighbor Embedding. In Becker, S., Thrun, S. & Obermayer, K. (eds.) *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 15 (MIT Press, 2002). URL <https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2002/file/6150ccc6069bea6b5716254057a194ef-Paper.pdf>.
- [12] Wang, Y., Huang, H., Rudin, C. & Shaposhnik, Y. Understanding How Dimension Reduction Tools Work: An Empirical Approach to Deciphering t-SNE, UMAP, TriMap, and PaCMAP for Data Visualization. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **22**, 1–73 (2021). URL <http://jmlr.org/papers/v22/20-1061.html>.
- [13] Amid, E. & Warmuth, M. K. TriMap: Large-scale Dimensionality Reduction Using Triplets (2020). URL <https://openreview.net/forum?id=BkeOp6EKDH>.
- [14] Font, F. & Bandiera, G. Freesound Explorer: Make Music While Discovering Freesound! Tech. Rep. URL <https://freesound.org/docs/api/>.
- [15] Audio Commons - Timbral explorer. URL <https://www.audiocommons.org/2019/01/30/timbral-explorer.html>.
- [16] Heise, S., Hlatky, M. & Loviscach, J. SoundTorch: Quick Browsing in Large Audio Collections. In *Audio Engineering Society - 125th Audio Engineering Society Convention 2008*, vol. 2 (2008).
- [17] Kohonen, T. The self-organizing map. *Proceedings of the IEEE* **78**, 1464–1480 (1990).
- [18] Logan, B. Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients for Music Modeling. In *ISMIR* (2000).

- [19] Fried, O., Jin, Z., Oda, R. & Finkelstein, A. AudioQuilt: 2D Arrangements of Audio Samples using Metric Learning and Kernelized Sorting (2014).
- [20] Quadrianto, N., Smola, A. J., Song, L. & Tuytelaars, T. Kernelized Sorting. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* **32**, 1809–1821 (2010).
- [21] hawley, s., bagley, j., porter, b. & traynham, d. vibrary: a consumer-trainable music tagging utility. *journal of the audio engineering society* (2019).
- [22] Sononym - Searchable Sound. URL <https://www.sononym.net/>.
- [23] Kobel, M. The drum machine’s ear: XLN Audio’s drum sequencer XO and algorithmic listening. *Sound Studies* **5**, 201–204 (2019).
- [24] Atlas 2 Main - Algonaut. URL <https://algonaut.audio/>.
- [25] Garber, L., Ciccola, T. & Amusatogui, J. C. AudioStellar, an open source corpus-based musical instrument for latent sound structure discovery and sonic experimentation (2020).
- [26] Ester, M., Kriegel, H.-P., Sander, J. & Xu, X. A Density-Based Algorithm for Discovering Clusters in Large Spatial Databases with Noise. In *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, KDD’96*, 226–231 (AAAI Press, 1996).
- [27] COSMOS AI-Powered Sample Finder | Waves. URL <https://www.waves.com/plugins/cosmos-sample-finder#introducing-cosmos-sample-finder>.
- [28] Font, F., Serra, J. & Serra, X. Folksonomy-based tag recommendation for collaborative tagging systems (2013).
- [29] Green-Armytage, P. A Colour Alphabet and the Limits of Colour Coding. *JAIC - Journal of the International Colour Association* **5** (2010).
- [30] Glasbey, C., van der Heijden, G., Toh, V. F. K. & Gray, A. Colour displays for categorical images. *Color Research & Application* **32**, 304–309 (2007).

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- [31] Sharma, G., Wu, W. & Dalal, E. N. The CIEDE2000 color-difference formula: Implementation notes, supplementary test data, and mathematical observations. *Color Research & Application* **30**, 21–30 (2005).
- [32] Wad's Optimum 16 Color Palette. URL <http://alumni.media.mit.edu/~wad/color/palette.html>.